

Heterocyclic Compounds derived from 9-Amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene.

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That *o*-aminophenol forms the basis of syntheses of a number of heterocyclic compounds is well known. The object of the present investigation was to see if 9-amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene which, like *o*-aminophenol, has the hydroxy and amino-groups in *ortho*-position to each other could similarly be utilised for the formation of heterocyclic ring systems. With this object in view, the above phenanthrene derivative was condensed with various substances such as formic and acetic acids, benzamidine hydrochloride, *o*-phenylene diamine, toluylene diamine, 1:2-naphthylene diamine, benzaldehyde and alcoholic ammonia and the condensation products derived therefrom examined. The nature of the condensation product obtained in each case has been described in the experimental portion.

EXPERIMENTAL.

9-Amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene hydrochloride required for the purpose was prepared according to the method of Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3130).

Condensation with Formic Acid: Formation of Phenanthrozasole.

9-Amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene hydrochloride (1 g.) was heated under reflux with an excess of formic acid for 3 to 4 hours when a brown precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered from the solution and repeatedly, washed with water. The residue was found to be insoluble in most solvents. So it was boiled several times with alcohol and the residue (m.p. above 300°) which was of brown colour and micro-crystalline structure was analysed. (Found: N, 6.57. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{ON}$ requires N, 6.39 per cent.).

9-Amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene hydrochloride (1 g.) was heated under reflux with an excess of glacial acetic acid for 2 to 3 hours when a brick-red precipitate was obtained. It could not be further crystallised as it was found to be insoluble in almost all solvents. It was, therefore, successively washed several times with acetic acid and alcohol. So obtained it forms a brown crystalline powder, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 82·21; H, 4·93; N, 6·18. $C_{16}H_{11}ON$ requires C, 82·40; H, 4·72; N, 6·01; per cent.). This compound is quite different from those obtained by Pschorr (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2737) and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 8130) who from 9-amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene hydrochloride and acetic anhydride obtained two different acetyl derivatives.

9-Amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene Hydrochloride and Bensamidine Hydrochloride: Formation of N-Phenylphenanthriminazole.

The hydrochlorides of the two bases were thoroughly mixed together in molecular proportion and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 190-200° for about 4 hours. The mixture first melted and at the end of the reaction, solidified to a crystalline mass which was detached from the tube, finely powdered and then treated with boiling water. The residue was repeatedly boiled with alcohol and acetic acid and finally crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and water; m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 85·85; H, 4·68; N, 9·75. $C_{21}H_{14}N_2$ requires C, 85·71; H, 4·76; N, 9·52 per cent.).

9-Amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene Hydrochloride and o-Phenylene Diamine: Formation of Phenanthraphenazine.

A finely powdered mixture of *o*-phenylene diamine (1 g.), 9-amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene hydrochloride (2·5 g.) and fused zinc chloride (1 g.) was heated in a boiling tube in an oil-bath for about 4 hours at 175-180°. There was at first formed a molten semi-solid mass which ultimately formed into a soild cake. The soild melt was detached from the tube, finely powdered and boiled several times with water. It was next washed with acetic acid and was finally

crystallised from nitrobenzene in which it is fairly soluble. It forms green needles with a bright coppery lustre, m.p. above 300° . (Found: N, 3.85. $C_{23}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 3.65 per cent.). This compound is identical with that prepared by Bamberger and Grob (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 535).

Phenanthraxine.—When 9-amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene hydrochloride was heated in a sealed tube with alcoholic ammonia at $150-160^{\circ}$ for 4—5 hours it was converted into phenanthraxine. The reaction product was filtered from alcohol and the dirty brown residue was successively boiled with alcohol and acetic acid and finally extracted with boiling nitrobenzene from which on cooling a yellow micro-crystalline powder was obtained; m p. above 300° . (Found: N, 7.52. $C_{23}H_{16}N_2$ requires N, 7.37 per cent.). It is identical with the compound obtained by Bamberger and Grob (*loc. cit.*).

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